

GEO.INFORMED

GEO.INFORMED report

Use Case Description

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Author: Stien Heremans (INBO)

Project partners: KU Leuven FNL

KU Leuven PSI

Research Institute Nature and Forest (INBO), Brussels

Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek (VITO), Mol

Digitaal Vlaanderen

Contact: stien.heremans@inbo.be

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Use Case Description

Project Overview

GEO.INFORMED was a four-year strategic research project (2020–2024) funded by the Research Foundation Flanders (FWO). The initiative was formed as a consortium bringing together the scientific expertise of KU Leuven and VITO (Flemish Institute for Technological Research) with the domain knowledge of INBO (Research Institute for Nature and Forest) and the digital know-how of Digital Flanders.

The primary objective of GEO.INFORMED was to bridge the gap between rapidly advancing Earth Observation (EO) capabilities and the daily operational needs of Flemish policy makers. Traditionally, environmental monitoring in Flanders has relied on static, labor-intensive mapping cycles - such as the annual updates based on orthophotography or manual fieldwork. While valuable, these methods often fail to capture dynamic landscape changes, such as the rapid onset of droughts, the seasonality of temporary water bodies, or short-term agricultural activities like winter crop cultivation.

The project aimed to modernize this workflow by providing the end users with faster, more accurate, and automated intelligence. By leveraging these tools, policy makers can address urgent environmental issues with greater agility and precision.

The use cases of GEO.INFORMED

In the first project phase, we collected ‘use case’ proposals from within the environmental policy domain in Flanders (the northern part of Belgium) through an online survey. We define a ‘use case’ as a delineated set of parameters that support the same policy needs and share a common monitoring protocol. We only considered proposals that demonstrated a direct link to environmental monitoring and policy. Our survey yielded a total of 23 proposals, which we conceptually grouped into a longlist of 15 clearly delineated use cases.

In the second project phase, we assessed the feasibility of these 15 use cases. For each use case we assessed whether (i) the required information was spatially detectable from Sentinel data, (ii) the required information was spectro-temporally observable from Sentinel data, and (iii) a sufficient amount of reference data was available or could easily be obtained/collected. Each parameter could be scored either as insufficient (red flag), sufficient (orange flag) or good (green flag). As soon as a use case received either one red or two orange flags, it was considered as unfeasible and excluded from the implementation phase. As such, seven use cases were excluded and we ended up with a final shortlist of eight use cases.

Four of the final cases are primary cases, which constitute the core of the scientific trajectory of the project. The other four use cases are secondary cases, where the feasibility and thus uptake remains uncertain. Each case was assigned to one of the project partners, in close

collaboration with one or two end users. An overview of the partners and users assigned to each of the cases can be found in the table 1 below.

Table 1: Overview of the use cases, their type, the responsible project partner and the associated end user(s). KUL-PSI = KU Leuven – Processing Speech and Images, KUL-FNL = KU Leuven – Division Forest, Nature and Landscape, INBO = Research Institute Nature and Forest, VITO = Flemish Institute for Technological Research, ANB = Agency for Nature and Forests , VLM = Flemish Land Agency , VMM = Flemish Environment Agency.

Use case	Type	Project partner	End user(s)
1 - Biological valuation map	primary	KUL-PSI	INBO
2 - Forest monitoring	primary	KUL-FNL	INBO
3 - Wild boar damage	secondary	KUL-FNL	ANB / INBO
4 - Pavement 5 meter zone	secondary	KUL-PSI	VMM
5 - Catch crops	primary	INBO	VLM / VMM
6 - Algae bloom	secondary	VITO	VMM
7 - Fire hazard	secondary	INBO	ANB
8 - Water detection	primary	VITO	ANB / INBO

Use case 1: Biological valuation map (primary case)

The Biological valuation map (BVM) is a uniform map of land cover and vegetation types in Flanders, based on fieldwork. The land cover and vegetation types are defined in an extensive list of mapping units. It serves as a reference map for open spaces for anyone involved in nature conservation, spatial planning, environmental reporting, and landscape design in Flanders.

The primary application of the BVM, along with the associated mapping of Natura 2000 habitats, is the implementation of the European "Habitats Directive." According to this directive, member states must provide an updated map of protected habitats to the EU every six years.

Benjamin Descamps' master's thesis (2019)¹ revealed that the BVM is a well-known tool at the local policy level (cities and municipalities). Larger cities, in particular, use this map regularly in their daily operations. However, the long update cycle and the fact that not all areas are updated regularly undermine local administrations' trust in the BVM.

The update of the BVM for the entire Flemish region is included in the policy note 2019-2024 by the Flemish Minister for Environment, Zuhal Demir. This goal has been translated into a horizontal project in the Strategic Multi-Year Planning of INBO.

The goal of this use case is to perform a pixel classification (semantic segmentation) of the entire Flemish region into BVM mapping units (or higher hierarchical levels).

For the latest version of the BVM (version 2020), approximately 170,000 hectares were mapped across Flanders, of which 68,000 hectares have been mapped within Special Protection Areas (SBZ) since 2016. This data can be used to train deep learning models. Outside SBZ, we can utilize alternative data sources such as agricultural registration and the Large-Scale Reference Database (GRB).

¹ Descamps B (2019). De Biologische Waarderingskaart - Onderzoek naar het gebruik van een Vlaams beleidsinstrument door lokale besturen [Master's thesis,UGent]

Use case 2: Forest monitoring (primary case)

Information on tree species is important to support policy, management, and research. The Forest Inventory of Flanders delivers crucial ground-based measurements on the status and long-term evolution of forests in Flanders. However, such measurements only allow for statistical evaluation over longer time periods on the regional scale of Flanders. In this context, satellite-based approaches offer the opportunity to generate maps containing up-to-date and spatially-explicit information on forests. In this use case, the core objective is to generate maps of frequently-occurring tree species in Flanders with satellite time series.

The stakeholders are interested in the state and evolutions in forests in Flanders. Particularly, they are interested in the conversion from conifer to broadleaved stands. Although specific percentages of mixture are pursued, it is not always clear whether those targets are met.

The stakeholders are also interested in knowing how specific conifer species are doing in the forests and in updating the 1990/2000 forest stand map (NL: Bosreferentiaalag), which has not been updated since it was first created.

The main source of reference data for this use case is the Regional Forest Inventory of Flanders, collected by ANB (Agency for Nature and Forests) of the Flemish Government. For this use case, data from the second (2009-2019) and the third (2019-present) monitoring cycle are available.

This is a policy-supporting network for all forests in Flanders and is legally supported in the Forest Decree (Art. 41 quarter). Spatially, the sampling design is based on a fixed grid of 0.5 by 1 km over Flanders. This yields 27,163 points of which roughly one tenth (2700 plots) are located within forests. In time, one measurement cycle takes 10 years, meaning that each plot is visited every 10 years. Each year, roughly one tenth of the plots are visited. Each plot is visited at least twice, once in summer for vegetation measurements and one in winter for dendrological measurements.

Use case 3: Wild boar damage (secondary case)

In the past 15 years, the wild boar population in Flanders has significantly increased. Wild boars can cause considerable damage to agricultural crops, leading to substantial costs for farmers. The Flemish Government is responsible for policies related to wildlife damage, but there is a lack of supporting data. We do not have a clear understanding of the extent of crop damage caused by wild boar in Flanders or where it is occurring.

Since September 1, 2009, the Decree of the Flemish Government regarding compensation for wildlife damage caused by non-huntable wildlife and compensation for damage caused by protected species has been in effect. This decree regulates the administrative procedure for compensating significant damage caused by non-huntable wildlife (implementation of Article 25 of the Hunting Decree) or by a protected species (implementation of Article 52 of the Nature Decree).

Ideally, we would have access to a dashboard with damage indicators that show in which parcels damage has occurred and the extent of that damage. Remote sensing can help us (i) quickly detect damage and (ii) accurately estimate the percentage of damage within a parcel.

Through the damage reporting system, farmers can report wildlife damage. However, there is no compensation if the damage is caused by non-protected species, so not much is reported through this system. There is also no verification of the reports submitted via the damage portal. For 2018, 245 reports were submitted, for 2019, 952, and for 2020, 267.

From Anneleen Rutten's PhD research (University of Antwerp), we have access to drone images of damaged and undamaged plots. There are images available from 133 damaged plots, which include both grasslands and cornfields. These images can be used to derive reference data through pixel or object classification. Random forest models with an accuracy of over 90% and a kappa value above 0.80 have already been developed based on this data.

To collect additional recent data, we will need to gather new data ourselves (using a drone) or utilize reports submitted to ANB or the hunting sector (via the WILDER app). However, the latter does not provide an objective estimate of the percentage of damage nor data on undamaged plots (absence data).

Use case 4: Pavement in the 5 meter zone (secondary case)

This case focuses on enforcement, a priority in the Flemish government agreement. The 2019-2024 Environmental Policy Note emphasizes enforcement as a key component of a robust environmental policy. One of the operational objectives is to focus on qualitative reporting and evaluation of environmental enforcement. Additionally, an environmental enforcement program will be developed in 2021, setting out the policy objectives for the coming years in an integrated manner.

Constructing new structures within 5 meters of public waterways is prohibited. Yet, new violations are detected every year, often involving individuals who had previously received this information. Waterways frequently run along the backs of properties, making them invisible from public roads. As a result, violations are often only discovered during the annual inspection of the waterway, by which time the structure is already completed and in use.

Detecting such violations more quickly would mitigate the consequences for offenders and reduce the misconception of impunity among potential violators. This would contribute to the policy objectives of the Flemish government, the goals of integrated water management, and the Blue Deal initiative.

To effectively manage environmental enforcement, it is important to detect new constructions and hard surfaces early. Additionally, detecting "changes" such as elevations or bare soil can help authorities take action before hard surfaces or permanent structures are added. This proactive approach would prevent the need to wait until hardening is fully implemented, allowing for earlier intervention.

By identifying these changes early through remote sensing or other monitoring technologies, authorities can intervene more quickly, mitigating potential violations and ensuring compliance with regulations related to land use and environmental management.

The Flemish Environmental Agency (VMM) monitors the 5-meter zone around public waterways twice a year, and there is data on violations stored in the VMM database. In addition to this, there are more general datasets from which we can infer locations that have been hardened, such as the Large-Scale Reference Database (GRB) and VITO's land use map. These datasets can also be used to detect bare soil.

We will need to verify whether the GRB includes the date of construction, as this would allow us to train models using data from just before a hard surface was installed. This would improve our ability to detect changes in land use early and act proactively, helping with enforcement and compliance.

Use case 5: Catch crops (primary case)

The MAP-6 (Manure Action Plan-6) framework, which regulates the use of fertilizers in Flanders, stipulates that farmers must grow cover crops during the winter period. These are crops planted after the main crop to prevent or reduce nutrient leaching, particularly nitrates. Examples of such cover crops include winter rye, radish, kale, and ryegrass. Farms in Flanders are assigned a specific target area for cover crops that they must plant each year.

The Flemish Land Agency (Vlaamse Landmaatschappij) is responsible for verifying whether this target area is actually achieved and whether the sowing and harvesting periods are respected.

The presence of a cover crop at the level of an individual plot during the designated period, with additional information on the sowing and harvesting dates (with the highest possible temporal accuracy), is critical for monitoring compliance with the MAP-6 regulations. This requires precise data on when the cover crop was planted and harvested, ensuring that these actions occurred within the allowed timeframes.

To achieve this, remote sensing technologies, such as satellite imagery or drones, can be employed to track changes in vegetation. Coupled with data from farmers or automated systems that log planting and harvesting activities, we can develop a system that accurately monitors the presence of cover crops and the compliance with the regulatory periods. This would ensure better enforcement and adherence to the MAP-6 requirements.

Quite some reference data are available for this use case. Through the annual unified application from the Department of Agriculture and Fisheries (DLV), all farmers are required to register their plots and specify which crops they will cultivate that year. This includes the cover crops, along with their sowing and harvesting dates. Both the DLV and the Flemish Land Agency (VLM) conduct annual checks to verify the accuracy and completeness of the declarations made in the unified application, for both main and secondary crops.

Use case 6: Algae blooms (secondary case)

This use case contributes to the implementation of the Water Framework Directive. Blue-green algae blooms float on the water's surface, forming a blue-green, sometimes reddish-brown, oily layer. As the layer thickens and the algae cluster together more densely, the algae die off, releasing toxins that can be harmful to both humans and animals.

On one hand, blue-green algae blooms are monitored in swimming zones and recreational ponds because they pose a health risk to swimmers and recreational users. On the other hand, the Flemish Environmental Agency (VMM) also monitors algae blooms in other waterways when they are reported. This use case can help develop an early warning system to detect algae blooms more quickly, allowing for faster precautionary measures to be taken.

By implementing early detection systems, such as remote sensing or water quality monitoring technologies, authorities could identify high-risk areas sooner, enabling faster response and reducing the potential health risks for humans and ecological damage to water bodies. To detect the potential presence of blue-green algae (cyanobacteria), the parameters expected by the Flemish Environmental Agency (VMM) are (i) the (potential) presence of blue-green algae and (ii) cyanobacteria concentrations. For effective policy support, these maps should be updated as frequent as possible—ideally near real-time—to allow for timely interventions and preventive measures.

Achieving this level of detection could involve using satellite-based remote sensing for water quality, combined with local sensors that can detect changes in water conditions. Algorithms that analyze parameters such as chlorophyll levels, water temperature, and nutrient concentrations could also enhance the accuracy of cyanobacteria detection and concentration estimates. The available reference data includes the location and date of algae bloom events. Since 2016, there have been 278 events reported (of which 26 were confirmed as 'no cyanobacteria').

Other potentially interesting reference data sources include:

Internet of Water Flanders: Currently providing data on electrical conductivity (EC) and temperature (T), with plans to later include pH and nitrate levels, especially if data is collected from larger water bodies.

- Photos of algae blooms collected via an app at the INBO (Research Institute for Nature and Forest).
- Measurements from De Vlaamse Waterweg (e.g., Roeselare-Leie).
- www.waterinfo.be: A comprehensive platform for water-related data in Flanders.

These datasets can provide valuable input for building a robust detection and early warning system for algae blooms by correlating environmental factors like temperature, pH, and oxygen concentration with the occurrence of blooms. Combining them with real-time data and historical records can enhance predictive models for timely intervention.

Use case 7: Fire hazard (secondary case)

The Agency for Nature and Forests is responsible for fire prevention in nature and forest areas (based on color codes). An important parameter in heathland areas that can be used to assess fire risk is the presence of purple moor grass (Molinia). Studies, including in the United Kingdom, show that the "fuel load" of heathlands is higher when purple moor grass is present, particularly when in a dried-out state.

In cases of eutrophication due to atmospheric nitrogen deposition or accelerated and increased mineralization of organic material caused by drainage and drought, purple moor grass spreads quickly and eventually dominates the entire vegetation. This can lead to a fire hazard.

The aim of this use case is to monitor/map the presence (and biomass) of purple moor grass (Molinia) in fire-prone (heathland) areas in Flanders.

In the Biological Valuation Map, "Grassed heathland (dominance of purple moor grass)" is classified as a separate category, and these locations could potentially be used as a reference for this use case. To support the six-yearly reporting on habitat quality, INBO (Research Institute for Nature and Forest) started a monitoring network in 2014 to assess the local conservation status of Natura 2000 habitats. This network consists of a set of permanent vegetation plots (PQs) where parameters related to vegetation composition and structure are measured.

Habitat structure is assessed in circular plots with a radius of 18 meters, and vegetation composition is recorded in square plots of 3x3 meters for open habitats. The network includes approximately 170 survey locations per habitat type, with oversampling within Special Protection Areas (SBZs), which are selected from the habitat map of Flanders. Each location is revisited every 12 years, using a rotational design where 1/12th of the plots are measured each year. Grass encroachment is an important indicator here, and it is closely linked to the presence of purple moor grass.

Use case 8: Water detection (primary case)

Standing waters have been underrepresented in environmental policy so far, partly because the data, particularly for smaller bodies of water, was fragmented. Yet, they make an essential contribution to water, carbon, and nutrient cycles, and are crucial for a significant portion of Flemish biodiversity. They are an important asset for climate adaptation and mitigation, especially in the fight against drought and water scarcity. For the past few years, a very detailed reference dataset of standing waters in Flanders has been available: the 'Watervlakken' (Water Bodies) map layer.

To optimally use this map layer for policy purposes, including efforts under the Blue Deal, it is necessary to keep it as complete and up-to-date as possible with a high refresh rate. Manual detailed revisions are labor-intensive, and sporadically reported updates are insufficient to maintain the dataset. Therefore, new techniques are needed to support the map's updates.

In addition to the permanent water bodies included in the 'Watervlakken' map, it is also valuable to generate an overview of locations where water stagnates for part of the year (especially during periods of waterlogging). These are the so-called 'water-holding depressions.'

It is important to inventory these water-holding depressions (in agricultural areas), as they are potential zones for the creation of infiltration ponds and possibly multi-purpose ponds. The significance lies in defining target zones for an improved infiltration policy. Within the framework of the Blue Deal and addressing drought issues, this is a key policy topic.

For updating the water bodies map, the main objectives are (i) detecting the disappearance of known water bodies and the emergence of new ones (change detection), (ii) assessing the location and delineation of water bodies (object segmentation).

For the inventory of water-holding depressions, the main aim is to (i) detect the presence of water surfaces after a specific event in time, for a specific area and (ii) detect changes over time in the presence of water surfaces. These outputs might help track dynamic changes in water bodies and monitor temporary water accumulations, which is vital for policies related to water management and drought mitigation.

In terms of reference data, there is an area-covering vector geodataset with all known, clearly delineated, and long-term standing water bodies in Flanders, created by INBO. However, for water-holding depressions in agricultural areas, no specific reference data have been collected. That said, permanent water-holding depressions are included in agricultural declarations. Therefore, the data from these agricultural declarations could potentially be used as reference data for this purpose.